

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECT OF WATER-TREATMENT CHEMICALS ON THE PROPERTIES OF CONCRETE

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of water- treatment chemicals on the properties of concrete; using two different brands of Ordinary Portland cement. The compressive strength of the concrete as the important property is taken as the index of its quality and the physical properties such as abrasion was checked. Concrete cubes were cast with Dangote and Ashaka Portland cement, cured in the solution of water-treatment chemicals (Aluminium sulphate and Calcium hypo-chloride) and crushed to obtain their compressive strengths. The results obtained were compared with the results of the compressive strengths of the control cubes cast with the two brands of Ordinary Portland cement cured in water for 28 days. The control cubes cast with Dangote cement attained 29.6N/mm² at 28 days hydration while 29.1 N/mm² was attained for cubes cast with Ashaka cement. Concrete cubes made with Dangote cement and cured in water-treatment chemicals attained the average strength of 29.4N/mm², 29.2N/mm² and 28.9N/mm² at 7 days, 14 days and 28 days curing age respectively while the strength of 28.6N/mm², 28.4N/mm² and 28.3N/mm² at 7, 14 and 28 days curing age was attained for the cubes made with Ashaka cement. The strength of the Dangote cubes cured in chemicals decreased from the control cubes by 0.8%, 1.5%, 2.1% from the control cubes at 7, 14 and 28 days curing while for the Ashaka cubes there was decrease in strength from the control cubes by 1.7%, 2.3% and 2.8% of the control cubes at 7, 14 and 28 days curing age respectively.

KEYWORDS: Ashaka cement, Portland cement, Aluminium sulphate, physical properties

INTRODUCTION

There are two commonly used structural materials which include concrete and steel in the construction of buildings, bridges, highways or dams. They sometimes compliment one another, and sometimes compete with one another, so that many structures of similar type and function can be built in either of these materials (Neville, 1996).

Concrete as the most widely used man-made construction material is second only to water as the most utilized substance on the planet (Gambhir, 2005). It is obtained by mixing cementitious material, water and aggregate (and sometimes admixtures) in required proportion. The mixture when placed in forms and allowed to cure hardens into a rock- like mass known as concrete.

In its hardened state, concrete should have the properties of strength, durability, impermeability, and it should have minimum dimensional changes. The strength, durability and other characteristics of concrete depends upon the properties of its ingredients, on the proportion of mix, the method of compaction and other controls during placing, compaction and curing. (Gambhir, 2005).

Among the various properties of the concrete, its compressive strength is considered to be the most important and is taken as an index of its overall quality. It has almost no tensile strength, (usually measured to be about 10 to 15 percent of its compressive strength) and for this reason it is almost never used without some form of reinforcing (Portland cement Association, (2005).

Though Concrete is a durable material requiring a little or no maintenance in normal conditions or environment, but when subjected to highly aggressive or hostile environment such as the presence of organic matter in the aggregates and the presence of aggressive chemicals and / or aggressive chemicals initiating substances in the environment, it

has been found to deteriorate resulting in pre-mature failure of structure or reached a state requiring costly repairs. (Moskvin, 1980 and Taylor, 1977).

Concrete as stipulated by (Gambhir,2005) is not entirely impervious to moisture and other soluble salts and one of the main characteristics influencing the durability of concrete is its impermeability to ingress of water, oxygen, carbon dioxide, chloride, sulphate and other potentially deleterious substances.

Engineers' have taken full advantage of concrete's superior engineering properties and have used it to build water retaining structure. These concrete water treatment tanks or dams are constantly subjected to an environment containing dissolved salts and chemicals used for water treatment. These chemicals include Aluminium sulphate, Calcium hypo-chloride and calcium hydroxide (Andrew, 1995).

According to Edwards (2002), aluminium sulphate $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ is a widely used industrial chemical and is sometimes referred to as alum. It is used in water purification to cause impurities to coagulate which are removed as the particles settles to the bottom of the container. The process is called coagulation or flocculation and the particles are removed by sedimentation and filtration. (Alexander, 1976).

Calcium hypo-chloride $Ca(ClO)_2$ also known as bleach is applied to water in treatment plants to react and destroy pathogens which also reduce bacteria in water. This chemical reacts in water to form hypo-chlorous acid and calcium hydroxide (American Concrete Institute, 2000).

Calcium hydroxide $Ca(OH)_2$ also known as hydrated limes is used in the treatment of potable water because of its strong basic properties for pH correction. (Halstead, 1957).

The water treatment chemicals which are soluble in water produce ions which create an entirely new chemical environment for the concrete. Investigation of the effects of these chemicals on the properties of concrete enables a wider knowledge on the resultant of their reaction at an early stage and over a long time (Shetty, 2004)).

OBJECTIVES

- (i) Identify the chemicals used for water treatment.
- (ii) Prepare the solution of these chemicals to treat water at worst turbidity.
- (iii) Prepare concrete cubes and cure them in the chemical.
- (iv) Determine the strength of concrete at 7, 14 and 28 days.
- (v) Compare the results with the control cubes.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Concrete cubes were cast with two different brands of Ordinary Portland cement (OPC), which include Ashaka Ordinary Portland cement and Dangote Ordinary Portland cement. The cubes were cured in chemicals used for water treatment.

The water treatment chemicals used are Aluminium sulphate and calcium hypo chloride, this does not include calcium hydroxide which will not be used mainly due to the fact that the P^H value of the water lies between 6.7 to 8.5.

Compressive strength test was carried out on the concrete cube subjected to water treatment chemicals at intervals of 7 days, 14 days, and 28 days.

The results of the compressive strength test was compared with the result of the compressive strength test for the controlled concrete cubes which were cast with the two different brands of Ordinary Portland cement and cured in portable drinking water for 28 days.

The study is essentially a laboratory based research; therefore concrete specimens were prepared using two brands of Ordinary Portland Cement namely: Dangote and Ashaka.

Aggregate

Aggregate used are classified as fine and coarse aggregate. The fine aggregate are those that pass through the 4.75mm BS (British Standard) test sieve, while those that are retained on the 4.75mm BS sieve are referred to as coarse aggregate. The aggregates were obtained from local suppliers within Yola metropolis and both complying with grading requirements of BS 882 part 2 (1973).

(i) **Fine aggregate**

The sand used for the concrete specimens falls under the classification of S. U. that is uniformly – graded sand. The fine aggregate was thoroughly cleaned and any deleterious materials likely to affect the properties of concrete removed.

(ii) **Coarse aggregate**

Natural stones were used as coarse aggregate in the study. The coarse aggregate was evaluated according to BS 882 part 2 (1973). The aggregate conforms to the requirement of the nominal size of graded aggregate.

Water

Potable drinking water was used for mixing and curing the concrete specimens.

Preparation of Specimen

For the purpose of this study/research, concrete mix design of 1 : 2 : 4 with water/cement ratio of 0.5 was used. The materials used were batched by volume and mixing was carried out manually and separately for each of the Ordinary Portland Cement OPC under laboratory conditions.

150mm x 150mm x 150mm metal moulds with oil smeared on the inside of the mould to avoid sticking was used for casting the concrete specimen after obtaining a uniform and consistent mixture. Vibration to remove entrapped voids was done manually and the concrete specimens were left in the mould for 24 hrs after casting before they were removed from the mould.

Sample Techniques

(i) For each of the brand of Ordinary Portland cement, OPC, 12 cubes of concrete specimen were cast and cured at three different ages in the prepared water – treatment chemical.

Table I: Number of Cubes vs. Brand of Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC).

Curing Age	Dangote cement	Ashaka Cement
7 days	3 cubes	3
14 days	3	3
28 days	3	3
Controlled cubes	3	3
Total	12 cubes	12 cubes

From Table 1, a total number of 24 cubes were cast

- (i) Three concrete cubes were cast as control specimen for each of the brand of Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) and cured in Portable drinking water for 28 days. Their compressive strength was determined.
- (ii) The concrete specimens were cured in water –treatment chemical prepared for worst turbidity. All the cured samples were subjected to compressive strength test.

Water – Treatment Chemicals

Aluminium sulphate (Alum) and calcium hypo-chloride (chlorine) were used essentially for the research. For the purification of water, at 160 NTU (Nepheametric turbidity unit), i. e the worst turbidity, the alum dose is 300kg

alum mixed in 9000 litre of water. Therefore for 1 litre of untreated/unpurified water, the alum dose will be equal to:

$$\frac{300 \times 1000}{9000} = 33.3333 \text{ g/l}$$

100 litre of untreated water was used for curing. The required alum dose = 3333.3333g = 3.3kg.

The chlorine dose is 5mg/litres. Therefore for the 100 litres, of chlorine dose will be = 100 x 5 = 500mg.

Compressive Strength of Concrete

Compressive strength test was carried out on the concrete in

Order to ascertain the concrete strength of the concrete subjected to the presence of aluminium sulphate and calcium hypo-chloride. The concrete specimens were weighed in the laboratory and their density determined before they were crushed to obtain the compressive strengths.

PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

SIEVE ANALYSIS

The results of the sieve analysis for the fine and coarse aggregate are tabulated in Tables 2 and 3 respectively.

Table 2: Sieve Analysis of Fine Aggregate.

Sieve size (mm)	Weight of Material Retained (g)	Weight of Material Passing (g)	Percentage of Material Retained (%)	Percentage of Material Passing (%)
5.00	0.00	999.90	0.00	100
4.75	0.80	999.00	0.10	99.90
2.36	3.50	995.50	0.40	99.50
1.70	7.90	987.60	0.80	98.70
1.18	32.30	995.40	3.20	95.50
600 µm	206.20	749.20	20.62	74.90
300 µm	604.40	144.80	60.40	14.50
100 µm	136.30	8.50	13.60	0.90
Pan	8.50	-	0.90	-

Total mass of Material = 999.9g = 1000g

Table 3: Sieve analysis of Coarse Aggregate

Sieve size (mm)	Weight of Material Retained (g)	Weight of Material Passing (g)	Percentage of Material Retained (%)	Percentage of Material Passing (%)
37.50	0.00	997.50	0.00	100
19.00	12.69	984.81	1.27	98.73
13.20	94.25	890.50	9.45	89.28
9.50	265.50	625.06	26.62	62.66
6.70	623.20	1.86	62.48	1.86
Pan	1.86	-	1.86	-

Total mass of material=997.50g

Table 4: Compressive Strength of Concrete Cubes made with Dangote and Ashaka Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) at seven days curing in water-treatment chemicals

	DANGOTE			ASHAKA		
Water – Cement Ratio	0.5			0.5		
Samples	1	2	3	1	2	3
Weight (g)	8768	8820	8650	8440	8680	8450
Density (g/cm ³)	2.60	2.61	2.56	2.50	2.57	2.50
Dial Reading (KN)	655	666	662	650	646	638
Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)	29.1	29.6	29.4	28.9	28.7	28.3
Average Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)		29.4			28.6	

Table 5: Compressive Strength of Concrete Cubes made with Dangote and Ashaka Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) at Fourteen days curing in Water – Treatment Chemicals

	DANGOTE			ASHAKA		
Water – Cement Ratio	0.50			0.50		
Samples	1	2	3	1	2	3
Weight (g)	8475	8335	8520	8210	8360	8320
Density (g/cm ³)	2.51	2.45	2.52	2.43	2.48	2.47
Dial Reading (KN)	659	662	655	645	637	639
Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)	29.3	29.4	29.1	28.6	28.3	28.4
Average Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)		29.2			28.4	

Table 6: Compressive Strength of Concrete Cubes made with Dangote and Ashaka Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) at Twenty Eight days curing in Water – Treatment Chemicals

	DANGOTE			ASHAKA		
Water – Cement Ratio	0.5			0.5		
Samples	1	2	3	1	2	3
Weight (g)	8850	8430	8430	8280	8330	8475
Density (g/cm ³)	2.62	2.49	2.50	2.45	2.47	2.51
Dial Reading (KN)	657	648	645	635	635	639
Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)	29.2	28.8	28.6	28.2	28.2	28.4
Average Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)		28.9			28.3	

Table 7: Compressive Strength of Concrete Cubes made with Dangote and Ashaka Ordinary Portland cement (OPC) at Twenty Eight days curing in portable drinking water.

	DANGOTE			ASHAKA		
Water – Cement Ratio	0.5			0.5		
Samples	1	2	3	1	2	3
Weight (g)	8960	8730	8980	8782	8820	8965
Density (g/cm ³)	2.65	2.59	2.66	2.60	2.61	2.66
Dial Reading (KN)	664	657	675	648	653	666
Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)	29.5	29.2	30	28.8	29.0	29.6
Average Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)		29.6			29.1	

FIGURE 1: BAR CHART REPRESENTING COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF CONCRETE CUBES MADE WITH DANGOTE PORTLAND CEMENT AND CURED IN WATER-TREATMENT CHEMICALS.

FIGURE 2: BAR CHART REPRESENTING COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF CONCRETE CUBES MADE WITH ASHAKA PORTLAND CEMENT AND CURED IN WATER TREATMENT CHEMICALS.

DISCUSSIONS

The compressive strength of concrete cubes made with Dangote and Ashaka Portland Cement, cured in portable drinking water for the period of 28 days is presented in table 4.6. Compressive strength of 30N/mm² was targeted for the cubes, but the average compressive strength of three samples of concrete cubes made with Dangote Portland Cement is 29.6N/mm² while the average compressive strength of the cubes made with Ashaka Portland Cement is 29.1N/mm². It has been observed from this test that there is a slight difference between the compressive strengths of the concrete cubes made with Dangote and Ashaka. This can be due to the difference in quality of the cement produced by these companies.

The concrete cubes cured in water – treatment chemicals for the duration of 7 days were observed to have dissolved salts i.e. a whitish appearance on the surfaces and there was no visible abrasion on the concrete surface. Consequently, for the cubes cured at the age of 14 days, the dissolved salt was noticed on the surfaces and there was no visible abrasion on the surfaces. But for the 28 days curing in chemicals, slight abrasion was noticed on the concrete edges as well as dissolved salts on the surface.

The results of the compressive strength test of the concrete cubes cured in water – treatment chemicals are shown in Tables 4, 5, and 6 for the curing age of 7 days, 14 days and 28 days respectively. From the data presented in the tables, it can be deduced that there was slight difference between the strength of the controlled concrete cubes cured in water and these in water– treatment chemicals. At the age of 7 days curing in water–treatment chemicals, for the concrete cubes made with Dangote Portland Cement, it was observed that there was a loss of strength up to about 0.8% of the controlled cube. For Ashaka Cement, there was about 1.7% loss of strength from the controlled cube. At the age of 14 days curing in the chemicals, it has been found that for concrete cubes made with Dangote there was about 1.5% of the average strength of the controlled cubes the reduction or loss of strength was about 2.3% of the controlled cubes. At the age of 28 days curing in chemicals, it has been observed that for the Dangote concrete, the loss of compressive strength is about 2.1% from the strength of the controlled cube. Similarly, there was about 2.8% loss of strength from the controlled cube for the Ashaka concrete.

From the above results, it can be deduced that there is an effect of the water – treatment chemicals on concrete in terms of the compressive strength of concrete and its physical properties. But this effect has been observed to be very small or slight with respect to the ages or duration of the concrete in the chemical environment.

The concrete cubes made with Ashaka Portland Cement have also been observed to have less resistance to the chemicals as the percentage strength reduction is higher between the interval of 7 days, and 28 days than the cubes made with Dangote Portland Cement. It can be concluded that the type and quality of cement is one of the important

factors that affect the properties of concrete, especially when the concrete are constantly subjected to hostile environment.

The results presented in figures 1 and 2 gives a pictorial representation of the data obtained from the compressive strength test, it was observed that the strength of the concrete gradually decreased with increase in the curing age, that is the longer the curing age or period of time the concrete remains in the water-treatment chemicals the lesser its compressive strength.

CONCLUSIONS

The average compressive strength, Table 7 for three samples of concrete cubes made with Dangote Portland Cement and cured in portable drinking water show for 28 days is 29.6N/mm², while the three samples of concrete cubes made with Ashaka Cement attained the average compressive strength of 29.1N/mm². There is a slight difference between the compressive strength made with Dangote and that of Ashaka Cement due to the quality difference of the cement produced by these companies.

The concrete cubes cured in water-treatment chemicals were observed to have dissolved salts, that is a characteristic whitish appearance on the surfaces. There was no visible abrasion on the concrete surfaces except for the cubes cured in water-treatment chemicals for the duration of 28 days.

At 7 days curing in water-treatment chemicals, the compressive strength of concrete cubes made with Dangote cement was observed to decrease from 29.6 N/mm² to 29.4 N/mm², which is about 0.8% loss of strength from the controlled cubes. While the cubes made with Ashaka cement decreased in strength from 29.1N/mm² to 28.6 N/mm² which is about 1.7% loss of strength from the controlled cubes.

At 14 days curing in water-treatment chemicals, the compressive strength of the cubes made with Dangote cement decreased to 29.2N/mm² which is about 1.5% loss of strength from the controlled cubes. While for the cubes made Ashaka cement, the compressive strength decreased to 28.4N/mm² which is about 2.3% loss of strength from the controlled cubes.

At the age of 28 days curing in chemicals, the compressive strength of the Dangote cubes decreased to 28.9N/mm², which is about 2.1% loss of strength. While for the Ashaka cube, the strength decreased to 28.3N/mm², which is about 2.8% loss of strength from the controlled cubes.

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